

Review

Organizational Digital Transformation Readiness: An Exploratory Investigation

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Abstract: The widespread adoption of digital technologies across various aspects of society has led to the emergence of two highly context-dependent constructs that explain how businesses are getting ready for transformative digital processes: digital readiness and digital transformation (DT). However, assessing the extent to which an organization is ready to succeed in a DT initiative still requires further investigation. This research addresses this gap by working towards a practical definition and model of organizational digital transformation readiness (ODTR). The authors investigate how an organization's readiness for digital transformation should be conceptualized, assessed, and improved through a systematic literature review. This literature review covered the years 2004 to 2021, as well as articles published until May 2022. The search was conducted in the Web of Science database, as well as in the most important publishers' databases, resulting in 264 papers on "e-readiness", 72 articles on "digital transformation", and 8 articles on "digital transformation readiness". Based on this, some dimensions emerged as the most prominent for understanding how companies prepare for transformative digital processes, namely technological resources, business processes, management capability, human capability, and corporate culture, which highlights the multidisciplinary nature of ODTR. Furthermore, the literature review showed the similarity between e-readiness and digital readiness, allowing the assessment of an organization's maturity for digital transformation. The review synthesized the scientific literature on the readiness of organizations for digital transformation, allowing the proposition of an integrative framework to evaluate ODTR. Moreover, it allows the development of insights and recommendations for practices related to successful digital transformation initiatives. As this literature review has limitations related to its scope and search criteria, future studies can provide a broader investigation into how organizations respond to the challenge of DT and their respective readiness to do so in practice.

Keywords: digital transformation; digital transformation readiness; organizational digital transformation readiness; digital readiness; systematic literature review

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1. Introduction

Information and communication technology (ICT) is a fundamental structural part of modern society [1], playing a significant role in promoting socio-economic development [2,3]. In fact, in recent decades, significant advancements in ICT have made available several functionalities that have allowed firms to adapt their business infrastructure to an entirely new digital era [4]. Due to that, a new concept has recently emerged in academia and among practitioners, namely digital transformation (DT) [5]. DT is a social construction, implying a cultural transformation, since it represents a process of social interaction and collective learning by which people embrace and disseminate digital technologies [6]. The notion of DT has become ubiquitous and is often understood as a change in how a company employs digital technologies to develop new business models that help generate more value [7]. Indeed, the digital revolution has transformed the nature of many organizations by radically changing processes and business models in almost all industries [8]. In this

way, companies have made an effort to respond to the challenges of competition and globalization brought about by the rapid and profound changes resulting from digital technologies [9], being at risk of not being able to survive in the market if they do not do so [10]. Thus, DT has been an imperative for organizations to remain competitive in the current digital world [11].

However, to date, there is not a unique and commonly accepted definition for the construct of “digital transformation”, which is often viewed simplistically as an ongoing process of adopting emerging technologies for significant change [12]. In addition, although DT has emerged as a phenomenon in the Information Systems (IS) area in recent years [11], there are as yet few articles that jointly address the constructs needed to define organizational digital transformation readiness. However, understanding the steps and background needed to successfully implement DT in organizations is crucial in an increasingly ICT-dependent world. Thus, for DT initiatives to be successful in companies, they must be adequately ready for it [13].

The term “readiness” refers to “the state of being ready or prepared for something” [14], describing a forward-looking state for something that is coming or has almost arrived [15]. E-readiness specifically represents the transformation of society to deal with complex issues related to the digital world [16]. In fact, since its inception, the concept of e-readiness has encompassed a wide range of definitions and different measurement methods, involving various approaches and results [17–20]. In fact, successful organizational DT initiatives require companies to be ready to implement or develop different capabilities, according to the business context in which they operate [9,21,22].

Moreover, so far, some questions regarding DT in organizations have lacked further development, remaining understudied [7,11,23–26], including the following: How do DT initiatives take place in organizations? What organizational requirements (resources, capabilities, and processes) are needed, and what is the sequence of actions to promote successful DT in organizations? In line with this, the object of this study is to investigate the following question: What do companies need to succeed in DT initiatives, that is to say, how to assess the DT readiness of organizations? Thus, to contribute to the extant literature on the subject, this article aims to review the topic of DT readiness and propose a framework for successful implementation of DT initiatives in organizations. From this perspective, a range of definitions, concepts, and connections referring to what is understood by DT, with a focus on organizations, will be analyzed.

2. The Foundations of Digital Transformation

According to its most basic meaning, transformation refers to “a complete change in somebody/something” [27]. In this sense, the DT construct would encompass a complete change by means of digital devices, technologies, and/or contexts. In the early 1950s, in one of the first publications that mentioned DT, the expression was approached in a very basic way, far from the complexity that has been assigned to it recently. Davis [28] p. 90 proposed that “a great deal of progress has been made in converting analog data into a useful digital form for data processing. The way in which this analog to DT is accomplished is not biased by tradition or legal reasons”. As society evolved, with the fast-growing use of digital technologies not only in machines or industries but in the most trivial aspects of daily life, the construct gained multifaceted approaches in the scientific literature, with several definitions that emerged in association with its use as a buzzword and are affecting its credibility and causing turmoil in both academic and practitioner fields [29].

The literature on DT is quite diverse, involving several knowledge areas, which has led the construct to not have a consolidated definition yet [25]. The initial studies on DT were related to the strategic role that ICT used to play to support business strategies [30]. As DT has different meanings for different audiences, this concept has not been equably applied in the Information Systems (IS) literature, being so associated with different perspectives [15]. Probably one of the most comprehensive works on the concept of DT was carried out by Vial [11] p. 118, who defined DT as “a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering

significant changes in its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies". After that, research on DT began to associate it with ICT-enabled transformation [5], namely DT started being perceived as an evolution of IT-enabled transformation, as it represented how digital technologies disruptively impacted individuals, organizations and society [11]. Another conceptualization commonly related to DT relates to innovation and disruption, understanding DT as a broader process of change that represents a combined effect that both drives and is driven by innovations and digital disruptions [31].

Although DT is a global phenomenon, each country can offer a more or less favorable context for such initiatives to be successful [32]. In addition, it is not only nations but also companies that face the challenges related to DT, which is dependent on three dimensions: technological, organizational, and social [6]. As noticed in previous studies [11,33], DT was primarily related to organizations, and there are significant contrasts throughout definitions concerning the sorts of advancements of technologies encompassed and the nature of the existing transformation [11]. In fact, DT is strongly related to organizations, addressing and emphasizing the impact of ICT on organizational structure, work routines, information flows, and managerial capabilities [11,23,34]. However, DT is a process adopted by companies to achieve superior performance and sustainable competitive advantage, through the convergence of multiple digital technologies capable of transforming various organizational dimensions, such as business models, customer experiences, and operations, thus configuring a significant change in ways of working [35]. DT is therefore associated with a profound transformation in organizations provided by digital technologies, aiming to radically improve their performance [8,36,37].

Moreover, Verhoef et al. [38] point out three external factors as the main drivers of DT: (1) the growing number of emerging technologies, (2) the drastic change in competition, and (3) the change in consumer behavior as a response to the digital revolution. However, despite the growing awareness of the importance of DT in reshaping organizational models and activities, many companies still struggle to assimilate and implement it accordingly [23]. Becoming digital is a ubiquitous challenge that has been faced by companies in the last few decades [39]. However, this transformation process is not sustained by technology alone [40]. Orlikowski [41] found empirical evidence that organizational transformation was enabled by ICT, but not caused by it. Thus, researchers and organizations gradually have perceived that DT is not only a technological shift [39]; it simultaneously impacts people and networks [35]. Previous studies have identified that successful DT initiatives are associated not only with the use of ICT but also with some other non-technology-related dimensions, such as culture and leadership [40]. Furthermore, both academics and practitioners have recognized the importance of human resources in this endeavor [29], and the lack of digital skills has been commonly pointed out as a hurdle to the success of DT [42]. Thus, the main critical success factor for DT initiatives is the focus on their transformational dimension rather than on digital issues [43]. This requires an alignment of ICT and people, so that the available digital potential is associated with skilled professionals, allowing DT to reach the best of its transformative power.

Although DT can be seen, from a business perspective, as a change in how companies use digital technologies to develop new business models, there has not been a multidisciplinary discussion on the subject. Insights about digital business strategy are still underdeveloped, as companies are still dealing with multiple digital shifts within traditional domains [4]. While it is difficult for researchers to develop theories, practitioners also face difficulties in developing and implementing DT strategies in their organizations [29]. In addition, there are different levels of DT in companies from different countries, although all have gone or will go through the same process [29]. Thus, it is plausible to realize that a more comprehensive understanding of the concept of DT, considering the context of organizations, is still in progress. Moreover, to understand how DT unfolds in organizations, it is necessary to assess their organizational readiness, namely their digital readiness, e-readiness, or, in a nutshell, their DT readiness, as addressed in the next section. Then,

in Section 4, the method used to conduct this research is explained, and, subsequently, in Section 5, we set forth the results obtained from the systematic literature review carried out with the aim of proposing and discussing, in Section 6, a framework for organizational digital transformation readiness, as well as the corresponding propositions derived from it. Then, in Section 6, we put forth the conclusions of this work, its theoretical and managerial implications, as well as the limitations of the research and the next steps to be conducted. Finally, in Appendix A, the PRISMA flow diagram used to carry out the systematic literature review on the topic under investigation is presented.

3. Conceptualizing e-Readiness and Digital Readiness

3.1. e-Readiness

The origin of the e-readiness construct is strongly related to the public dimension, addressing, for example, countries as units of analysis [42,44,45]. In fact, it stems from an attempt to provide a unified framework for assessing the scope of the digital divide between developed and developing countries [18]. In 1998, the Computer Systems Policy Project (CSPP), a public policy group, gathered information from technology companies in the United States and developed an e-readiness assessment tool known as the “Readiness Guide for Living in the Networked World”—the first time the term was applied [46]. However, the main problem with e-readiness is the lack of a common standard of assessment associated with a unified set of measures [47]. Jutla et al. [48] took the first steps in conceptualizing e-readiness from the competitive perspective of e-business. In addition, from an e-commerce perspective, Bui et al. [44] developed a framework to assess and monitor the e-readiness index of a country comprising eight factors—digital infrastructure, macroeconomics, investment capacity, education of citizens, competitiveness, access to skilled labor, culture, and cost of living—and 52 related indicators.

In the following years, several scholars attempted to critically assess the level of e-readiness in developing countries, such as Ramayah et al. [49], Ifinedo [50], Dada [45], Mutula and van Brakel [46], Alghamdi et al. [17], Al-Eryani and Rashed [51], and Chipembele and Bwalya [52], to name just a few. Dada [45] points out that several governmental and private institutions have formulated e-readiness rankings via different methodologies and divergent definitions of the construct. Thus, the results are not consistent with each other. Berthon et al. [53] offer a unique perspective on that, presenting a model in which 76% of a country’s e-readiness variation is explained by the propensity to corruption and cultural values. Lou and Goulding [54] also acknowledge the difference in methodologies and the divergent definitions of what is considered “global e-readiness”. In addition, they point out that the private sector initially conducted most e-readiness initiatives, as governments used to be late adopters of ICT strategies in general. Thus, very recent studies remain proposing and evaluating e-readiness measurement tools; as an example, a new review was conducted by Pal et al. [55], focusing on the agricultural sector.

3.2. Digital Readiness

Readiness is related to the condition of being fully prepared or willing to do something [14]. Thus, the concept of readiness can be described as the extent to which an organization is prepared to change its current state to a new desired state [56]. However, digital readiness construct has no universal definition [10,57], being an emerging construct derived from the concept of change readiness. One of the main contributions of research on digital readiness is the proposition of criteria for assessing organizational readiness for DT [58]. Digital readiness, thus, assesses the readiness of an organization before a DT endeavor is undertaken [59].

Although there are some differences, readiness is often used as a synonym for maturity [57]. Indeed, maturity models have been used to assess readiness, making it possible to identify an organization’s position in relation to a specific variable. In fact, they provide frameworks for assessing business performance, enabling comparison and improvement of an organization’s level of capability in a given dimension [59,60]. Digital readiness is

also a relevant competitive resource in an innovation economy as it affects the success of national R&D transfer to the entrepreneurial sector [61]. Companies looking forward to implementing DT initiatives must answer key questions about how to get started and which barriers can hamper the success of the DT endeavor [62,63]. These questions are directly related to the readiness of the company to be digitally transformed, focusing on its internal capabilities and barriers [64].

Moreover, De Carolis et al. [65] argue that previous models for measuring digital readiness are incomplete, as they do not consider the complexities of modern businesses. As such, they proposed a maturity model for digital readiness that measures the ability of companies to effectively manage their processes to achieve desired outcomes. However, the model proposed by De Carolis et al. [65] addresses the manufacturing sector. In the present study, the perspective is more closely related to the organizational business environment, which considers the human aspect as part of the fundamental characteristics for DT readiness in organizations. Some studies also analyze the relationship between digital readiness and technology acceptance in an individual approach, using the technology acceptance model (TAM) as a parameter [66,67]. However, in this study, the goal is to understand DT organizational readiness as a whole, taking into consideration human aspects [59].

In sum, in terms of conceptualization, the extant scientific literature does not indicate significant differences between e-readiness and digital readiness. Often both constructs are used to define a situation where a certain level of readiness is required to achieve a change from something analog to something electronic or digital. Indeed, the first studies on e-readiness considered the external environment, usually a country or nation, as the main antecedent for electronic adoption [18]. Over the years, there have been more articles published on e-readiness than on digital readiness—as it will be later demonstrated in this work—as digital readiness is a more recent issue related to the adoption of digital technologies by individuals, organizations, industries, and countries [10]. However, both constructs still lack a unified definition [10,45]. Based on that, in the extant literature, there is not enough empirical evidence to date on how to design and evaluate a successful DT in organizations from a business perspective. Therefore, there is a research gap on the exact understanding of organizational readiness for DT [37], which underpins the relevance of this work.

After addressing in the previous subsections, the concepts of e-readiness and digital readiness, as well as their entanglements, similarities, and differences, as proposed in the scientific literature, we present below the methodological procedure adopted to conduct this research and answer the abovementioned research questions.

4. Method

This study consisted of a systematic literature review to investigate the constructs that comprise organizational digital transformation readiness. To do that, we adopted the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis Protocol (PRISMA) to select articles and undertook thematic analysis to analyze the data collected [68–70].

The PRISMA flow diagram follows a four-step sequence, namely identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion, as detailed below [71].

Identification: In this phase, the research questions are identified, and relevant studies are sought. The search process should be systematic and comprehensive, with clear inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Screening: In this phase, the studies identified in the first phase are screened based on their relevance to the research question and the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This phase typically involves screening the titles and abstracts of the studies, followed by a full-text review of studies that meet the inclusion criteria.

Eligibility: In this phase, the eligibility of the studies that have passed the screening phase is assessed. This assessment includes evaluating the quality of the studies and their relevance to the research question.

Inclusion: In this phase, studies that meet the eligibility criteria are included in the systematic review. Data from these studies are extracted and analyzed, and the findings are synthesized and reported.

Below, the operationalization of the systematic literature review conducted is presented.

After having defined the research questions in the introduction section of the article, the review began with a selection of articles to identify the works published in related journals, including references that better matched the structure and discussion of the principal theme [72]. The data collection was carried out between April 2021 and May 2022. The review was conducted in chronological order, and the delimitation of the period comprised mainly the years 2004 to 2021, considering that the subject is still recent and practically unexpressed before this period. Articles published in 2022 were not included in the count shown in the graphs, in order to have equal comparison measures, i.e., using only complete years. Nevertheless, the articles published till May 2022 were reviewed for the overall analysis and for theoretical purposes. The search aimed to cover articles published in journals associated with the theme in the Web of Science database (although the SCOPUS database was also used in this review, it did not bring up any articles that had not already been obtained from the Web of Science database; therefore, it was decided to cite only the Web of Science database), as well as in the most important IS journals. The journals investigated were primarily in English, most of which with a double-blind review process. Books, technical reports, and other sources were excluded.

The first step addressed the search of the following constructs in the Web of Science database, using quotation marks to find the exact match of “digital transformation”, “e-readiness”, “digital readiness”, and “digital transformation readiness”. The search included the presence of the constructs in the title, abstract, and keywords to analyze and compare the number of papers published per year and in the sum of these years. Although there was a search for the total number of articles of the “digital transformation” construct, as the number of articles is much broader, the subsequent analyses were focused on the three other constructs: “e-readiness”, “digital readiness”, and “digital transformation readiness”. “Digital transformation” was used for the theoretical part, considering the relevance of the journals and the number of citations of the articles.

The second step comprised the analysis of the three aforementioned constructs/themes according to the areas of interest in which they were published (categories), allowing the identification of the main categories per theme. This categorization helped to prioritize the themes that are more related to IS, ICT, and other organizational themes.

The third step comprised the search for each of the constructs/themes in the related publishers of the most important journals between 2004 and 2022 in their specific databases, namely Elsevier Science Direct, Taylor & Francis, Springer, and Emerald. This stage aimed to evaluate the number of publications per theme and to find specific articles more closely related to DT readiness.

The last step included a deeper analysis of the main articles found, including the most cited and relevant ones, identifying those with a scope more closely related to organizations. The relevant themes related to DT readiness within the articles were then used to build a concept matrix to compare the findings in the literature. Further, a maturity model to assess the organizational DT readiness was proposed. Finally, a framework was developed to assess the organizational readiness for DT by investigating the logical order and connections of categorized themes selected in the reviewed articles. Thus, the DT initiative begins with the definition and evaluation of the organizational requirements necessary for this initiative to be successful [63].

In the appendix, the final flow diagram derived from the use of the PRISMA approach to conduct the systematic literature review is presented, as proposed by Page et al. [73].

5. Results

The search in the Web of Science and abovementioned publishers’ databases brought up works published from 2004 to 2021, considering both articles and conference papers.

Thus, 5007 articles related to “digital transformation”, 278 articles related to “e-readiness”, 91 articles related to “digital readiness”, and 7 articles related to “digital innovation readiness” were detected, when analyzing the title, abstract, and keywords of the surveyed works, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of articles by theme, 2004–2021. Source: Web of Science.

To focus on the “readiness” concept, the theme “digital transformation” was excluded from further analysis due to its broader scope, as it is inserted in various different academic categories. Figure 2 represents the search conducted, detailing the number of articles published on topics related to readiness, in chronological order and separated by year of publication. E-readiness is by far the most researched topic, totaling 278 articles in the period, covering mainly the governmental and institutional approach to readiness, and mainly addressing the metrics of stages and digital advances in countries. Although the concept “digital readiness” did not have the same numerical representation as “e-readiness”, it had the highest number of publications in a single year, 2021, reaching 36 articles, which highlights its recent growth and importance. For all themes, most articles were published from 2017 onwards.

Figure 2. Number of articles by theme by year of publication. Source: Web of Science.

Table 1 details the number of articles on each topic by Web of Science category in the period 2004–2021. The top twenty categories are listed in that table. It is relevant to mention that themes may be counted in more than one category, i.e., the theme “e-readiness” may

be considered in both the Business and Management categories so that the total sum of the categories may result in a much larger number than the original count of the articles. For e-readiness, the main categories are in the fields of Computer Science, Information Science, Business, Education, and Management; for digital readiness, the main categories are in the fields of Education, Management, Business, Computer Science, and Economics; and for DT readiness, the few articles found are divided into the fields of Business, Computer Science, and Economics.

Table 1. Number of articles in the main categories per theme. Source: Web of Science.

E-Readiness		Digital Readiness		Digital Transformation Readiness	
Computer Science Information Systems	54	Education Educational Research	24	Business	2
Information Science Library Science	47	Management	19	Computer Science Theory Methods	2
Business	40	Business	11	Economics	2
Education Educational Research	39	Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications	8	Automation Control Systems	1
Management	38	Economics	8	Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications	1
Computer Science Theory Methods	35	Engineering Manufacturing	8	Information Science Library Science	1
Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications	30	Computer Science Theory Methods	7	Management	1
Engineering Electrical Electronic	23	Environmental Sciences	7		
Computer Science Artificial Intelligence	18	Green Sustainable Science Technology	6		
Computer Science Software Engineering	13	Engineering Industrial	5		
Economics	12	Environmental Studies	5		
Telecommunications	12	Information Science Library Science	5		
Multidisciplinary Sciences	11	Computer Science Information Systems	4		
Engineering Industrial Operations Research	10	Automation Control Systems	3		
Management Science	10	Computer Science Artificial Intelligence	3		
Public Administration	9	Computer Science Software Engineering	3		
Engineering Multidisciplinary	8	Energy Fuels	3		
Political Science	7	Engineering Electrical Electronic	3		
Communication	6	Health Care Sciences Services	3		
Social Sciences Interdisciplinary	6	Operations Research Management Science	3		
Computer Science Hardware Architecture	6	Business Finance	2		

In this study, the focus is on articles related to organizational issues, thus covering the areas of Information Systems, Business, and Management.

As presented in Table 2, a complementary online search conducted on the main publishers’ databases from 2004 to 2022 nominated the journals with higher numbers of articles, resulting in 264 papers on “e-readiness”, 72 articles on “digital transformation”, and 8 articles on “digital transformation readiness”. The table is ranked from the highest to

the lowest number of articles found, ordered first by the “e-readiness” results, then by the subsequent two themes. Some of the main journals in the Information Systems and ICT subjects were marked in gray. The Information Systems Journal (ISJ), Information Systems Research (ISR), and Management Information Systems Quarterly (MISQ) do not present any articles related to any of the three abovementioned themes.

Table 2. Number of articles per theme by related journal.

	E-Readiness	Digital Readiness	Digital Transformation Readiness
The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries	48		
Government Information Quarterly	28	3	
Information Technology for Development	25	1	
International Journal of Information Management	13	3	
Journal of Global Information Technology Management	12		
Telecommunications Policy	11	4	
The Information Society	11	1	
International Journal of Electronic Commerce	10		
Telematics and Informatics	9		
IFAC-PapersOnLine	8	4	1
Procedia Computer Science	6	8	1
Industrial Marketing Management	6	3	
Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	6	2	
International Journal of Network Management	6		
Journal of Information Technology & Politics	6		
Information & Management	5		
International Information & Library Review	5		
International Journal of Public Administration	5		
Journal of Internet Commerce	5		
Technology in Society	4	2	
European Journal of Information Systems (EJIS)	4	1	
Cogent Business & Management	4		
Journal of Business Research	3	9	
Journal of Information Technology (JIT)	3		
Electronic Markets	3		
Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce	3		
Journal of Promotion Management	3		
Journal of Urban Technology	3		
Technovation	2	2	
International Journal of Project Management	2		

Table 2. Cont.

	E-Readiness	Digital Readiness	Digital Transformation Readiness
Journal of Strategic Information Systems (JSIS)	1	1	
Journal of the AIS (JAIS)	1		
Information Systems Management	1		
Journal of Marketing Management	1		
Technology Analysis & Strategic Management	1		
Procedia Manufacturing		10	
Technological Forecasting and Social Change		6	
Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology		3	
Journal of Manufacturing Systems		2	1
Computers & Industrial Engineering		2	
Computers in Industry		2	
Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management		2	
Journal of Management Information Systems (JMIS)		1	
Future Generation Computer Systems			1
Sustainable Production and Consumption			1
The Journal of Academic Librarianship			1
Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research			1
Information Systems Journal (ISJ)			
Information Systems Research (ISR)			
Management Information Systems Quarterly (MISQ)			
Total	264	72	7

After exploring the databases, a selection of the articles was made, prioritizing the ones addressing the “digital transformation readiness” (DTR) and “digital readiness” (DR) themes. The articles chosen were those most related to organizational/business aspects and with the highest number of citations.

Then, following the process described by Braun and Clark [74] and Braun et al. [75], an inductive thematic approach was used to identify, in each selected article, the common categories related to successful digital transformation initiatives. This process involved six steps: familiarization, generation, category search, category review, category definition and naming, and reporting. At the end of this process, twelve categories associated with successful digital transformation initiatives were identified, which were brought together in a matrix of concepts.

Table 3 presents the matrix of concepts, with the articles and the categories related to ODTR, which will be used to develop a framework on this subject. The table depicts the articles in chronological order and according to the number of related categories found in each article, from highest to lowest. In addition, the oldest article on the subject is from 2017, thus confirming the novelty of the theme. Therefore, the following categories were found, namely Technology, Change/Innovation/Disruption, Assessment/Maturity/Performance, Processes/Deployment/Implementation, Organization/Company/SME, Management/Strategy, Resources/Capabilities, Competitiveness, Business/Business Model, Culture/Environment, Human (Aspects), and Sustainability.

6. Organizational Digital Transformation Readiness (ODTR)

The literature review lists the main characteristics of the categories that make up organizational digital transformation readiness. Through an extensive search of terms related to e-readiness, digital readiness, and DT readiness, it was possible to verify that research on the latter subject is still scarce. Even in the organizational area, several articles are related to aspects of Industry 4.0 and manufacturing processes, leaving aside other business aspects. Thus, given the importance of the transformational processes that companies have been facing, with regard to the growing adoption of digital technologies, studies related to the subject under analysis are essential. However, before defining the architecture of the ODTR framework, it is essential to identify the key organizational processes for companies to achieve DT, as these business-related processes must portray the company's strategy [62].

Before designing the ODTR framework, it was necessary to define the maturity levels that would enable the company's readiness to change. The conceptualization of "maturity" is related to an organized set of levels to assess management practices in different capabilities or process areas in a qualitative or a semi-quantitative way [86,87]. Maturity models can be applied in different specific scopes, enabling a general understanding of what has to be done to develop a maturity assessment [86]. The levels proposed in this study were inspired by the CMMI framework (Capability Maturity Model Integration), which has its roots in the software engineering area—having been generalized to incorporate other areas—as well as the DREAMY maturity model [65,86]. The decision to use the CMMI framework was based on the clear, flexible, and well-designed model, which provides a structure that helps organizations appraising their maturity, describing discrete levels of process improvement within each process area [87]. In this work, the CMMI maturity model was used [65] with some adjustments made to fit organizational digital readiness assumptions in order to consider socioeconomic differences, as many businesses in developing countries would start at Level 0, rather than Level 1, as some models propose, as detailed later.

Figure 3 describes the maturity levels for ODTR, according to the CMMI model [87] and considering adaptations provided by De Carolis et al. [65], as mentioned above. At Level 0 (incomplete), the process is unpredictable, poorly controlled, or without any control; the management level is reactive and with inconsistent performance. Level 1 (initial) embraces an initial approach to meeting the objectives of the practice area, beginning to address performance issues. Level 2 (managed) includes the practices from Level 1, establishing a complete set of practices that fully address the intent of the practice area, requiring no specific assets and identifying and monitoring the progress. Level 3 (defined) incorporates Level 2 practices, adding organizational standards to address specific characteristics, using and contributing to organizational assets, and focusing on achieving performances. Level 4 (integrated and interoperable) incorporates Level 3 practices, with integration and interoperability of applications, as well as information exchange, being thoroughly planned and implemented considering enabling technologies, and uses quantitative techniques to understand performance and achieve quality; finally, Level 5 (digital-oriented) builds on Level 4 practices with a fully digital-oriented process, based on robust technological infrastructure and a high potential organizational growth, providing fast and secure information exchange, in collaboration with the company functions and decision making.

Figure 3. Maturity levels for organizational digital transformation readiness. Adapted from CMMI Team [87] p. 13 and De Carolis et al. [65] p. 17.

Differently from the DREAMY (digital readiness assessment maturity model) approach, presented by De Carolis et al. [65], as well as other models in the literature that prioritize relevant stages for manufacturing processes [13,77], this study focuses on the organizational approach, also considering human aspects as essential to enable ODTR. Thus, the aforementioned categories are grouped via categorical content analysis [88], seeking to develop a parsimonious framework related to organizational digital transformation readiness, the key dimensions of which are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. Dimensions and criteria associated with ODTR.

Dimensions	Criteria
Technological Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology availability (infrastructure to support digital processes) - Use of BI, data-driven, digital tools for management - Innovative TR
Business Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Processes to support digital businesses - Evaluation processes to guarantee digital evolution of businesses
Management Capability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management and Leadership Skills on digital environment - Develop and implement digital environment and businesses as core strategy - Innovation driven mindset - Ability to evaluate performance indicators to provide sustainable businesses
Human Capability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human digital skills development - Ability to work with digital resources - Understand and disseminate digital culture
Corporate Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Culture of digital environment - Competitive awareness - Sustainable digital business culture - Corporate institutional communication to disseminate digital culture

Those dimensions encompass the indispensable resources and capabilities related to organizational digital readiness, representing the success factors for DT endeavors. Each dimension and criterium must be evaluated according to the previous maturity levels

proposed to achieve digital readiness. The dimensions and the subsequent criteria are as follows:

Technological resources comprise available technology (infrastructure to support digital processes), use of business intelligence (BI), and other data-oriented digital management tools, as well as innovative IT solutions such as cloud computing, big data, the internet of things (IoT), virtual/augmented reality, robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning (deep) [64,65,78,84]. They include, via categorical analysis [89], the categories Technology and Resources/Capability.

Business processes encompass all the processes needed to support digital businesses. DT requires a change in organizational processes and/or the development of new business models [9]. The processes are carried out via digital platforms and consist of well-designed and -described formal procedures that may be divided into several sub-processes. In addition, processes must be constantly evaluated to guarantee the digital evolution of the business [64,78,79]. They include, via categorical analysis [89], the categories Assessment/Maturity/Performance and Processes/Deployment/Implementation.

Management capability encompasses management and leadership skills in the digital environment. This includes the development and implementation of a digital environment and definition of a digital business model as a core strategy. Managers must also have an innovation-driven mindset, capable of perceiving digital changes in a competitive environment. This dimension also refers to the managerial ability to evaluate performance indicators to provide a sustainable digital business [13,64,84]. It includes, via categorical analysis [89], the categories Organization/Company/SME, Management/Strategy, Competitiveness, and Business/Business Model.

Human capability is related to the development of digital skills of personnel directly or indirectly related to tasks that demand digital knowledge. These skills are usually verified in hiring processes or can be developed through specific training programs. Not only employees but also third parties must have the ability to work with digital resources. Another aspect of human capability is the understanding and dissemination of the organization's digital culture [13,59,78,84]. It includes, via categorical analysis [89], the category Human (Aspects).

Corporate culture encompasses the development and perpetuation of a digital environment throughout all corporate levels by means of institutional communication and actions. As organizations understand the need to perform in a digital competitive scenario, they seek to promote a sustainable digital culture, namely an innovative culture. Stoianova et al. [64] merged corporate culture and human resources into one dimension. However, corporate culture is a broader concept, integrating human resources, processes, management, physical organizational aspects, and technology [13,64,84]. It includes, via categorical analysis [89], the categories Change/Innovation/Disruption, Culture/Environment, and Sustainability.

The ODTR Framework

From the theoretical background presented and the analysis of the key constructs and organizational dimensions related to digital readiness, the organizational digital transformation readiness (ODTR) framework is proposed, as detailed in Figure 4.

The framework proposes a logical and structured approach to assess an organization's readiness to undertake a successful digital transformation initiative, addressing three levels of analysis, namely the macro-, meso-, and micro-levels. The framework begins at the macro-level, covering the market and the context in which the company operates, called the competitive environment. The meso-level—the focus of the study—is the organization itself, which is analyzed through its key dimensions related to DT readiness, namely technological resources, business processes, capacity management, human capacity, and corporate culture, previously detailed. These key dimensions, which represent the micro-level of analysis, do not follow a pre-defined hierarchy or order, interacting with each other and being guided by top management.

As mentioned earlier, each abovementioned organizational dimension needs to reach the required maturity to lead to the achievement of the required digital readiness for a successful digital transformation. At the organizational level, once the levels of maturity of the five key dimensions have been reached, it is up to top management to propose, develop, and implement a digital strategy that translates into a digital transformation (Schallmo et al. [57]; Bican and Brem [83]; Correani et al. [90]).

Figure 4. Organizational digital transformation readiness (ODTR) framework.

According to Rauser [91], digital strategy refers to the strategy a company would apply to all of its digital initiatives. This includes the entire process: collecting all required information, planning, identifying risks and opportunities, maintaining your digital strategy, and creating sub-strategies such as your digital-marketing strategy. In the same vein, Schallmo et al. [57] argue that a digital strategy summarizes digital transformation processes, objectives, guidelines, and controlling structures and acts as interface to the coordination of the numerous digitalization activities. In addition, the digital strategy contains a company’s digital vision and expresses the business strategy’s objectives and priorities through digital plans. Moreover, for Schallmo et al. [57], within the digital strategy, digital technologies and methods are applied to products, services, processes, and business models. In order to develop a digital strategy, the company and its environment have to be analyzed as a basis for several future scenarios. Therefore, the digital strategy of a company should comprise its vision, mission, values, strategic objectives, as well as the corresponding key success factors and indicators.

Thus, the digital strategy (according to Schallmmo et al. (2018) [57], the terms digital strategy, digitalization strategy, digital business strategy, digitization strategy, and digital transformation strategy are used often interchangeably) will interact with all processes and digital resources previously listed, and its design will be determined by the level of digital innovation intended by the organization in its competitive environment. It is important to emphasize that, over the process, the DT readiness indicators must be monitored and controlled, until all levels for a complete DT are reached. Therefore, DT will take place when the necessary readiness is achieved. Once the transformation occurs, it consequently impacts the organization (as indicated by the arrow from the DT box towards the organization box). In addition, once the organization is transformed, it also impacts the competitive environment in which it is inserted (as indicated by the arrow from the DT

box to the competitive environment box). In this way, the framework portrays a cyclical feedback process where all levels of analysis can interact with each other, given the constant technological changes that occur in society today.

When assessing the DT readiness of companies in different socioeconomic realities, through the ODTR framework, three propositions can be formulated:

P1. Successful DT initiatives in organizations depend directly on their digital readiness, measured through their level of maturity in the ensuing dimensions: technological resources, business processes, management capacity, human capacity, and corporate culture [58,59,64,65,78,92].

That proposition, to be further tested, can be divided into five sub-propositions, namely:

P1a. The level of maturity of technological resources influences successful DT initiatives in organizations.

P1b. The level of maturity of business processes influences successful DT initiatives in organizations.

P1c. The level of maturity of management capacity influences successful DT initiatives in organizations.

P1d. The level of maturity of human capacity influences successful DT initiatives in organizations.

P1e. The level of maturity of corporate culture influences successful DT initiatives in organizations.

P2. The level of readiness of firms for DT has a direct impact on the conceptualization, design, and implementation of their digital strategies [78,79,92].

P3. The level of maturity for DT of a business directly impacts its level of competitiveness in the market in which it operates [64,78,79].

7. Conclusions

This study proposed an integrative framework for assessing the ODTR based on a review and analysis of the extant scientific literature on this subject. Having done that, this paper revealed an overlap between the definitions of e-readiness and digital readiness constructs. Indeed, the extant scientific literature does not demonstrate so far a significant distinction between e-readiness and digital readiness, as both are supposed to indicate the level of maturity required from a country, institution, organization, or person to be digitally transformed successfully. This work also unveiled the lack of a unified and monosemic definition for the “digital transformation readiness” construct, especially in the organizational realm. In the universe of articles retrieved from the Web of Science and publishers’ databases, e-readiness represents about 74% of the works, digital readiness represents 24%, and digital transform readiness represents only 2% of the articles, most of them published after 2017.

Indeed, ODTR is a relatively new construct in the academic realm, reporting the idea of measuring the level of readiness of an organization for ICT implementation and use, combined with other organizational issues, to enable a successful DT. In fact, studies on organizational readiness for DT are also quite scarce, representing a research opportunity. In short, there is an academic gap associated with the investigation of the level of maturity required for the various dimensions of an organization for the success of DT initiatives carried out in it, as corroborated by the literature review. This academic gap ranges from the assessment of the existing context for organizational DT initiatives to their implementation and final assessment.

It is also noteworthy that there are several relevant concepts involved with organizational readiness for DT, as already mentioned, which is corroborated by evidence found in related systematic literature reviews as well as explicitly stated by Latifah et al. [69] and Silva et al. [93]. These concepts are related not only to ICT but also to several other organizational dimensions, such as resources, processes, organizational culture and environment, competitiveness, management, human competencies, business models, and sustainability,

among others, thus confirming the multidisciplinary (and also the interdisciplinarity) of the theme.

7.1. Theoretical Contributions

As a first theoretical contribution, this study provided a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the concepts and methodological aspects that cover the topic of ODTR. Indeed, the literature review conducted identified the main constructs related to digital transformation organizational readiness—namely, technological resources, business processes, management capability, human capability, and corporate culture.

Furthermore, the article unveiled the logical configuration of the critical factors associated with successful DT initiatives in organizations, which allowed the formulation of an exploratory framework on this topic. This proposed framework articulates the main dimensions and criteria necessary to measure and evaluate the organizational readiness for DT, in line with the ideas of [94,95]. It also provides a straightforward visualization of the essential steps required in an organization to develop a digital strategy associated with its DT, in accordance with [96]. Moreover, the theoretical framework also includes a competitive environment perspective, proposing that the DT process is cyclical: once the transformation is accomplished in the organization, it impacts the competitive environment in which the organization operates in return, which is also supported by Fabac [97].

Another theoretical contribution of this work is the development of a maturity model to assess organizational digital readiness, as also suggested by Gökalp and Martinez [98] and Kao et al. [99]. This maturity model allows for conceptual adjustments that suit organizational assumptions and various socioeconomic scenarios.

7.2. Practical Contributions

In addition to the theoretical contributions mentioned, this work also makes some practical contributions. The first of these concerns the main dimensions that an organization must pay attention to in order to achieve successful digital transformation initiatives. In fact, adequate technological capabilities spanning emerging technologies (such as the IoT, Blockchain, generative AI, etc.) as well as established technologies (such as databases, intranets/extranets, IOS, etc.) are necessary for successful DT efforts. Furthermore, managers must also be aware of the need for new business processes that duly correspond with the technologies available for DT initiatives. Furthermore, the management team must be trained to deal with the peculiarities of digital transformation initiatives, especially regarding leadership issues. In line with this, capacity building efforts must be undertaken by organizations so that their personnel are well equipped to deal with DT projects. Finally, it is essential that organizations have a corporate culture that welcomes innovation and tolerates possible failures arising from the implementation of DT projects.

Another practical contribution of this work is the possibility for organizations to assess *ex ante* their readiness for a successful implementation of DT via the ODTR framework. Thus, managers can anticipate which features should be improved in companies so that possible DT initiatives are successful.

7.3. Limitations and Further Steps

While this review is not exhaustive, the proposed framework is intended to provide a broader understanding of the steps an organization must take to succeed in a DT initiative in a fast-changing digital-dependent world. However, some limitations must be considered. The search was limited to the Web of Science and main publishers in IS and Management databases. Although this allowed a broad search, some publications may not have been considered. In addition, some limitations were established regarding the scope and search criteria adopted.

Future steps of this research may include further elaboration and validation of the proposed model, with a broader investigation on how organizations have responded to the challenge of DT and their readiness in practice to do so, in line with what was developed

by Soto-Acosta [100]. Moreover, comparative studies might also incorporate specific contextual aspects associated with distinct business industries in different socioeconomic contexts, such as ODTR in developing countries, as also proposed by Raghavan et al. [101]. In addition, further investigations can strengthen the understanding of how (and by whom) some relevant decisions about DT initiatives are made in organizations, addressing the role and importance of leadership and employees’ digital readiness for successful digital transformation initiatives, as also suggested by Larjovuori et al. and Höyng and Lau [102,103]. Finally, future research could expand the current debate on new business models enabled by DT, namely how companies can change their basis of competition associated with innovative products and services through digital transformation.

Overall, with the accelerated pace of digital technologies and the profound changes that the world has faced lately, expanding the theoretical scope associated with the impact of emerging ICT on organizations is essential to monitor and evaluate the latest initiatives on DT, as well as to predict future changes. This work, therefore, intends to move in this direction, by proposing a new way of conceptualizing and evaluating the processes behind the DT initiatives that organizations are currently experiencing.

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Appendix A

Figure A1. PRISMA flow diagram for the systematic literature review. Source: Page et al. (2021) [73].

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